

Microwave vs. conventional sintering of alumina-based castable containing ZnO: energy efficiency and properties changes

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ABSTRACT

Balancing industrial operations with environmental conservation stands as a challenge in the 21st century. In this context, employing microwaves for ceramic sintering proves advantageous compared to conventional methods, diminishing lead time, improving mechanical properties, and requiring less power. However, this sintering method remains underexplored due to limited knowledge about refractory phases capable of effectively interacting with electromagnetic radiation. This study addresses the potential of using ZnO as a microwave absorber in Al₂O₃-based refractories, comparing microwave-sintered castables with electric-heated counterparts treated thermally up to 1700 °C. While the ZnO content (11.4 wt%) remained stable in the electric-heated furnace, significant evaporation occurred in samples microwaved above 1300 °C. The mechanisms behind this phenomenon and strategies to mitigate it are discussed. Additionally, microwave sintering demonstrated benefits such as a denser microstructure with uniformly scattered open pores, enhanced mechanical properties at room temperature, a 26-fold faster lead time, and an estimated 70% lower energy consumption. Thus, this sintering method presents a promising alternative to enhance refractory manufacturing efficiency, reducing environmental impacts and production costs.

Keywords: Sintering; Microwave; Castable; Refractories; ZnO; Energy Efficiency.

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12 de abril de 2024 às 09:02

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